

Experiments on the Synthesis of Santenone. Part I.

A Synthesis of Homosantenic Acid.

BY SURESH CHANDRA SEN-GUPTA.

1-Santenone (IX) occurs in Indian sandalwood oil (*Schimmel's Report*, 1910, Oct., p. 98) and the inactive form has been prepared by Semmler and Barteltt (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4467) by the oxidation of π -norborneol with chromic acid and also by Aschan (*Ofvers. Finska Vet. Soc.*, 1910, 53 A, No. 8, p.17) by the oxidation of sentene with potassium dichromate-sulphuric acid mixture, the latter reaction involving a Wagner rearrangement.

The constitution of santenone has been established by its oxidation to santenic acid (X) recently synthesised by Komppa (*Ber.*, 1932, 65, 1710). No work on the synthesis of santenone has as yet been attempted. The present investigation has been undertaken with a view to synthesise the ketone and this has been attempted following Ruzicka's synthesis of fenchone (*Ber.*, 1917, 50, 1362).

Ethyl levulinate and ethyl α -bromopropionate were condensed by Reformatsky's reaction giving the lactone of ethyl β -hydroxy- $\alpha\beta$ -dimethyl adipate (I), which was converted into the cyano-ester (II) by means of potassium cyanide and the latter on hydrolysis and esterification by the alcohol vapour method gave ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dimethylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (III). This tricarboxylic ester by the application of Dieckmann reaction with molecular sodium was converted into ethyl 2:3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3:5-dicarboxylate (IV), the latter on hydrolysis gave 2:3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid; the ethyl ester (V) of this keto acid condensed with bromoacetic ester in presence of zinc giving the hydroxy ester (VI). This on dehydration with phosphorus oxychloride gave the unsaturated dehydrohomosantenic ester (VII) which on reduction and hydrolysis yielded homosantenic acid. Work is in progress on the synthesis of santenone by the distillation of the lead salt of homosantenic acid.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Lactone of ethyl β -hydroxy- $\alpha\beta$ -dimethyladipate (I).—Ethyl levulinate (108 g.), ethyl α -bromopropionate (137 g.) and zinc wool (50 g.), diluted with dry benzene (250 c.c.) were heated on the water-bath till the exothermic reaction commenced. When the brisk action subsided, the reaction was finally completed by heating on the water-bath for 1 hour; the product was decomposed with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer separated, washed with caustic soda solution and water, dried with calcium chloride, benzene removed, when the lactonic ester distilled as a thin colourless oil, b.p. 148-49°/8 mm., yield 90 g. (Found: C, 59.7; H, 8.1. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dimethylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate (III).—The lactonic ester (90 g.) and finely powdered potassium cyanide (43 g.) were heated under reflux for 10 hours at 200-20°. The brown reaction product was hydrolysed by heating with 350 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid for 10 hours. The solution was evaporated on the water-bath almost to dryness, the residue thoroughly extracted with ether, dried, ether removed. Through a hot solution of the residue in absolute alcohol (200 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) was passed alcoholic vapour from 2 litres of alcohol. The alcohol was distilled off, the solution diluted with water, extracted with ether, dried, ether removed and distilled. Repeated fractionation of the portion collected at 130-160°/5 mm. gave 40 g. of the ester at 147-52°/5 mm. It is a light-coloured thin liquid. (Found: C, 59.3; H, 8.7. $C_{15}H_{26}O_6$ requires C, 59.6; H, 8.6 per cent).

Ethyl 2:3-dimethylcyclopentanone-3:5-dicarboxylate (IV) was prepared by heating the tricarboxylic ester (35.5 g.) with molecular sodium (3.5 g.) in dry benzene (150 c.c.) for 1 hour on the water-bath, whereby the sodium quickly dissolved. The light-coloured clear liquid was cooled, decomposed with ice, shaken with dilute sulphuric acid and the benzene extract washed, dried, benzene completely removed and distilled, when it collected at 145-50°/5 mm. It gave strong ferric chloride coloration, yield 20 g. (Found: C, 61.0; H, 7.9. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

2:3-Dimethylcyclopentanone-3-carboxylic acid was prepared by heating the foregoing keto-dicarboxylic ester (20 g.) with concentrated hydrochloric acid (35 c.c.) and water (100 c.c.) for 5 hours.

The clear aqueous solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and repeatedly extracted with ether, the ethereal solution dried and the solvent removed. On distillation a small fraction (2 g.), b.p. 100-150°/5 mm. evidently consisting of the ester, was obtained along with a large fraction (11 g. of the pure acid) of a colourless thick liquid, b.p. 150-53°/5 mm. (Found: C, 61.3; H, 7.8. $C_8H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 61.5; H, 7.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* was prepared in aqueous solution and crystallised from water or dilute alcohol, m.p. 208°. (Found: C, 50.4; H, 6.9. $C_9H_{15}O_3N_3$ requires C, 50.7; H, 7.0 per cent).

The ethyl ester (V).—The acid (10 g.) was heated for 14 hours with a solution of sodium (1.8 g.) in absolute alcohol and ethyl iodide (13 g.). Alcohol was distilled off, the residue diluted with water and repeatedly extracted with ether, dried, ether removed, when the ester distilled almost completely at 105-106°/5 mm. as a colourless mobile oil, yield 9 g. (Found: C, 65.1; H, 8.7. $C_{10}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 65.2; H, 8.7 per cent).

The *semicarbazone* crystallised from methyl alcohol in colourless prismatic needles, m.p. 191°. (Found: C, 54.4; H, 7.9. $C_{11}H_{19}O_3N_3$ requires C, 54.8; H, 7.9 per cent).

Ethyl dehydrohomosantenate (VII).—Ethyl dimethylcyclopentanonecarboxylate (12 g.), ethyl bromoacetate (12 g.) and zinc wool (6 g.) diluted with benzene (50 c.c.) were heated on the water-bath with the addition of a crystal of iodine until the vigorous reaction set in. It was finally heated on the water-bath for 1 hour to complete the reaction. After treating with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid, the benzene layer was washed with caustic soda solution, dried and distilled, when the unchanged keto-ester (1.6 g.) collected at 100-20°/4 mm. and a colourless oil (8.4 g.) at 125-50°/4 mm. consisting of the oxy- and the dehydro-ester. This was completely converted into the unsaturated ester by heating on the water-bath with phosphorus oxychloride (3 g.) in dry benzene (40 c.c.) for 3 hours. This benzene solution was successively treated with cold water and dilute caustic soda, dried and distilled, when 6.5 g. of a pleasant smelling liquid collected at 125-30°/4 mm. It decolourised bromine water readily. (Found: C, 65.6; H, 8.6. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 66.1; H, 8.7 per cent).

Homosantenic ester (VIII).—The dehydro-ester (5 g.) dissolved in absolute ether (25 c.c.) was reduced with hydrogen in presence of platinum oxide catalyst (3 g.) under atmospheric pressure. It

absorbed the calculated amount of hydrogen in about 2 hours and boiled at $130-35^{\circ}/5$ mm. (Found: C, 65.4; H, 9.5. $C_{14}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 65.6; H, 9.4 per cent).

Homosantenic acid.—The free acid was obtained by hydrolysing the ester with alcoholic potash, evaporating off the solvent, and the residue, dissolved in a small amount of water, was acidified with hydrochloric acid, when the homosantenic acid immediately separated out. On repeated crystallisation from water it was obtained as almost colourless needles, m.p. 170° . (Found: C, 60.3; H, 7.9. $C_{10}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 60.0; H, 8.0 per cent).

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CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
PRESIDENCY COLLEGE,
CALCUTTA.

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